

EDU REKHA INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ARTS, LAW AND SOCIAL SCIENCE

Journal Homepage: <https://edurekhapublisher.com/erijals/>

Volume- 2 Issue – 3 (May-June) 2026

ISSN: 3107-5169 (Online)

Frequency: Bimonthly

PAGES: 105-111

ARTICLE TITLE:

ISSN: 3107-5169

EDU REKHA INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ARTS, LAW AND SOCIAL SCIENCE (ERIJALSS)

Law & social science, anthropology, business studies, communication studies, corporate governance, criminology, cross-cultural studies, demography, development studies, economics, education, ethics geography, history, industrial relations, information science, international relations, law, health, linguistics

JOIN US

+91 8658576262

edurekhapublisher.com

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION AND NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT: A PHILOSOPHICAL EXAMINATION OF CONCEPTS, ROLES AND CHALLENGES

AUDU, Nancwat Montex, PhD

Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education and extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.

ARTICLE HISTORY

RECEIVED

17-06-2026

ACCEPTED

24-06-2026

PUBLISHED

29-06-2026

Corresponding author:

AUDU, Nancwat Montex, PhD

Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education and extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.

Abstract

The main thrust of this paper was to examine the meaning, roles, justification and challenges of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria. The paper described an entrepreneur as someone who ventures by taking risks into planning, organizing and coordinating a business to make profit by either producing goods or rendering services. Entrepreneurship education is defined as a process of adjustment which involves the development of the social and economic efficiency of individuals by upgrading their thought pattern, and focusing on training students on how to develop positive attitudes, innovations and skills for self-reliance. National development is described as the change in growth and development of a country which includes social, cultural and economic change observable in equal living standard for all, equal distribution of income and capital, expansion of facilities – health, education, infrastructures among others. Promotion of economic development by increasing Gross Domestic Product, creation of immediate large scale employment and reduction in Rural – Urban drift etc are identified as role of entrepreneurship to national development. Low competence of entrepreneurship education lecturers, absence of curricular capacity to support training, non-favourable policy environment among others are identified as challenges of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria. Creation of entrepreneurship friendly environment by the government, development of entrepreneur internship programme, establishment of an enterprise college are among others suggested for tackling challenges of entrepreneurship in Nigeria.

Keywords: Entrepreneur, Education, Entrepreneurship education, National development

Introduction

Man is basically a metaphysical being. Man in his ingenuity has adopted education as instrument per excellence to translate his metaphysical beliefs for his benefits. Education is the most effective means available to society to challenge the future. In all societies of the world education takes the centre stage in the arenas of self-realization, improved human relationships, individual capacity development, and national development. Education is one of the social institutions through which nations turn their population into assets and therefore one of the institutions that contributes to national consciousness, national unity, and social, cultural, economic, political, scientific and technological progress. Education will obviously not solve all the problems that humanity faces but it is still essential in its effort to connecting the members of the society, generate new relationships with respect to environmental needs. School instruction or the formal education is not everything. Education also values the role of the family and community and includes the non- formal and informal sides. The immense contributions of educators have not sufficiently been used to develop the entrepreneurial mind set for younger generation yet the younger generation are very crucial human resource whose contributions are very useful in all local communities.

Objectives of the Study

1. To explain the concept of entrepreneurship education
2. To define and describe who an entrepreneur is
3. To identify the skills and competencies required for entrepreneurship education
4. To examine the contributions of entrepreneurship education to national development
5. To investigate the challenges confronting entrepreneurship education in Nigeria
6. To proffer solution to the challenges confronting entrepreneurship education in Nigeria

Research Questions

The questions for the study are as follows:

1. What is entrepreneurship education?
2. Who is an entrepreneur and how can one become an entrepreneur?
3. What are the skills and competences needed for entrepreneurship education?
4. How does entrepreneurship education contribute to national development?
5. What are the issues and challenges confronting entrepreneurship education in Nigeria?
6. What are the solutions to the challenges of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria?

Methodology

The study adopted the three modes of philosophical study: the speculative, prescriptive and analytic modes.

Speculative Mode: Literarily, speculation is a process of thinking or meditating on a subject. It is the act of or process of reasoning apriori from premises given or assumed. The speculative method was applied to raise series of questions on definitions, meanings of concepts and ideas in the study.

Analytic Mode: To analyze means to make relevant distinction. Analytic mode enables one to dissect or separate aspects or elements

of an issue. This mode was engaged in the study to clarify the meanings of definitions, beliefs, concepts and propositions and also bring to focus the implications and challenges of entrepreneurship education on the development of Nigeria.

Prescriptive Mode: The Prescriptive method falls within the domain of ethics. Philosophy of education after performing its speculative function on problems and issues through vigorous definition, interpretation and analysis conclude by prescribing or recommending what is considered good or right or what is to be avoided as bad or wrong in educational practice. This method was used to make suggestions or recommendations to identified challenges of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria.

Concept of Entrepreneurship Education

One must not attempt to define entrepreneurship education without first define what education is. Generally education is described as the act or process of imparting or acquiring general knowledge, developing the powers of reasoning and judgment, and of preparing oneself or others intellectually for mature life. John Dewey (Wikipedia) conceives education as an enterprise which duly focuses on cultivating critical and reflective thinking as its most noble function. To him, an educated person is one who, first and foremost, has reached the stage of intellectual autonomy and can depend on this resource to lead a satisfying life consistent with his or her criteria of growth, both at the personal and the social level. What is Dewey implying? To him the acquisition just skills and knowledge does translate to education. Dewey, while not rejecting transmission of knowledge as a legitimate function of education, contends that its legitimacy resides in serving as the working capital of inquiry. Whitehead's (from Wikipedia) on his part perspectives education as the art of the utilization of knowledge. It is an idea or information that is useful or productive to the extent that it is put to use in the solution of problems. So any education that is not put to use in proffering solutions to problems faced by its recipient is no education by implication?

What is entrepreneurship education? To answer this question is to first describe who an entrepreneur is. An entrepreneur is someone who ventures, by taking risks, into a business involving planning, organizing and coordinating the use of materials and money to make a profit by producing goods or rendering services (Singh & Sharma, 2011). The entrepreneur is a risk taker and it is envisaged that the risk taking behaviour is informed through training and understanding of the business terrain. He is by and large someone that is never satisfied with the status quo, someone who is willing and able to convert new ideas or invention into a successful innovation. He is someone who perceives a business opportunity through risks analyses and takes advantage of the situation to make a profit. Entrepreneurs are individuals who strike out on their own to form a business. They create their own businesses, usually in an area that interests them or in which they have a certain skill set (Entrepreneurs, 2019). This business can be anything, from a new restaurant to an online home-made crafts shop. The level of success or money made does not define who is and isn't an entrepreneur. Small business owners and founders of multi-million-dollar companies alike can be classified as entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship on the other hand, is the service rendered by the entrepreneur (Zhou & Haixia 2012).

What is entrepreneurship education? Mauchi in Adenike., (2011) described Entrepreneurship Education (EE) as a form of education or

a process of adjustment which involves the development of the social and economic efficiency of individuals by progressively upgrading their thought pattern and eventually, their way of life. He reported that the objective of EEd is to provide individuals with the ability to recognize commercial opportunities and the knowledge, skills and attitudes to act on them. Oduwaiye also in Adenike observed that EEd focuses on assisting trainee students on how to develop positive attitudes, innovation and skills for self-reliance rather than depending on the government for employment. EEd seeks to empower students with new skills to be able to harness opportunities, be self-reliant and become job-creators and not job-seekers on graduation. European Union Commission (2018) sees entrepreneurship education as that form of education which prepares people to be responsible and enterprising individuals. It helps people develop the skills, knowledge, and attitudes necessary to achieve the goals they set out for themselves. Lee and Wong in Adenike assert that EEd is a catalyst for economic development and job creation in any society and therefore the teaching should be focused on elaborating this role.

Objectives of Entrepreneurial Education

Mauchi in Adenike., (2011) reported that the objective of EEd is to provide individuals with the ability to recognize commercial opportunities and the knowledge, skills and attitudes to act on them. (Okojie, 2009) reported that at inception, EEd was harped as the panacea for youth unemployment and a catalyst for sustained private sector-led growth. EEd was introduced to provide students in tertiary institutions with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of ventures.

Skills and Competencies required for Entrepreneurship Education

What are the requisite skills and competencies expected of who wants to be an entrepreneur?

UNESCO (2008) reported that entrepreneurs need determination as well as the ability to take risks, multi-task, and manage their time. Starting a business takes a lot of work, and the results can be unpredictable. Often, start-up entrepreneurs must work unstable hours and perform several or all of the tasks required to get their businesses off the ground. Additionally, they need to be detail-oriented in order to keep track of inventory and operations and to develop a business plan or investment proposal. Communication, customer service, and interpersonal skills can come in handy too, since an entrepreneur will need to reach out to customers, clients, partners, or other professionals involved in the business, such as suppliers. UNESCO (2008) further reported that entrepreneurs need determination as well as the ability to take risks, multi-task, and manage their time. Entrepreneurship is a skill that can be learnt. One does not have to be born an entrepreneur to run a successful business. One can become one by developing an entrepreneurial mindset and skills.

Educational Requirements and Tasks of Entrepreneurs

What is the job description of an entrepreneur, someone may ask? The job description of an entrepreneur is as varied as the entrepreneurs themselves (ENTREPRENEUR, 2019). The owner of a small business may perform many or all tasks having to do with his company, while the owner of a larger business may be able to afford to hire staff to do everything for him. Generally, an entrepreneur's main job is to make sure their business is turning a profit. ENTREPRENEURS(2019) reported the following as the tasks of entrepreneur: (i) Conducting market research for information about potential customers and

competition (ii) Writing a business plan for structure and to attract partners or investors (iii) Funding the business by raising money, appealing to investors, or taking a loan (iv) Choosing a location, whether physical or online (v) Getting the proper licenses and accounts in order to pay taxes and operate legally (vi) Developing and implementing a marketing plan to attract customers (vii) Hiring and managing employees.

Entrepreneurship Requirements: Education, Skills and Characteristics

What are the distinguishable requirements, skills and characteristic of entrepreneurs? It takes a certain skill set to succeed in self-employment. UNESCO (2008) reported that entrepreneurs need determination as well as the ability to take risks, multi-task, and manage their time. Starting a business takes a lot of work, and the results can be unpredictable. Often, start-up entrepreneurs must work unstable hours and perform several or all of the tasks required to get their businesses off the ground. Additionally, they need to be detail-oriented in order to keep track of inventory and operations and to develop a business plan or investment proposal. Communication, customer service, and interpersonal skills can come in handy too, since an entrepreneur will need to reach out to customers, clients, partners, or other professionals involved in the business, such as suppliers.

Concept of Entrepreneurship Education

EEd as a form of education is a process of adjustment. It involves the development of the social and economic efficiency of individuals by progressively upgrading their thought pattern and eventually, their way of life. Mauchi in Adenike., (2011) reported that the objective of EEd is to provide individuals with the ability to recognize commercial opportunities and the knowledge, skills and attitudes to act on them. Oduwaiye also in Adenike reported that EEd focuses on assisting trainee students on how to develop positive attitudes, innovation and skills for self-reliance rather than depending on the government for employment. EEd seeks to empower students with new skills to be able to harness opportunities, be self-reliant and become job-creators and not job-seekers on graduation. The training on EEd should therefore, be focused on developing capacities to collect, analyze, organize and critically evaluate information for business decision making. It was envisaged at conception, that entrepreneurship education will not only equip graduates with the skills and motivation for successful entrepreneurship, it was also to provide the needed prop to boost private sector investment to curb the problem of unemployment among school leavers. Dirk in Adenike reported that though education is the clearest path to individual opportunity and societal growth but, that, EEd is especially vital to supporting a more robust global economy. EEd inculcates new ideas to life through investments, creativity and value adding innovations (Okah and Odelola, 2009; Nwosu and Ohia 2009). At introduction in most European universities, EEd was focused to develop entrepreneurial capacities and mindsets of students (Wilson 2008). This purpose driven nature of EEd influences the curricula provisions of institutions in Europe. Lee and Wong in Adenike assert that EEd is a catalyst for economic development and job creation in any society and therefore the teaching should be focused on elaborating this role. Also, Akinkugbe in Adenike surmise that EEd introduction objective is to develop in graduates, the skills, entrepreneurial orientation and mindset to prepare for the

European Union Commission (2018) sees entrepreneurship education as that form of education which prepares people to be responsible and enterprising individuals. It helps people develop the skills, knowledge,

and attitudes necessary to achieve the goals they set out for themselves. Evidence also shows that people with entrepreneurial education are more employable. Entrepreneurship is a skill that can be learnt. One does not have to be born an entrepreneur to run a successful business. One can become one by developing an entrepreneurial mind set and skills.

Concept of National Development

The term 'National Development' is very broad and comprehensive. The term has been given several definitions by many different scholars. Generally it includes all aspects of the development of a nation namely, political, social, economic etc. It is a dynamic and revolutionary development of the society. According to John Vaizey in Sarma (2013), National development is the total effect of all citizens, forces and addition to stock of physical, human resources, knowledge and skill. National development is the change in growth and development, which includes social, cultural and economic change. It is the ability of a country to improve the social welfare of the people. National development would be the expansion and growth of people in a defined territory or government. Balaji (2018) reporting United Nation Organization (UNO) gave the factors necessary for National Development such as (a) Equal living standard for all, (b) Equal share of all in profit, (c) Equal distribution of income and capital, (d) Expansion of facilities regarding education, health, shelter and social welfare, (e) Preservation of environment. He went further to state that the primary factor used to distinguish developed countries from developing countries is the gross domestic product (GDP) per capita, that is, a tally of all the goods and services produced in a country in one year, expressed in U.S. dollars. GDP is calculated by dividing a country's GDP by its population. For example, a small country with a GDP of \$1 billion and a population of 50,000 has a GDP per capita of \$20,000. Some economists however prefer to see a per capita GDP of at least \$25,000 to be comfortable for declaring a country as developed. Many highly developed countries, including the United States, have high per capita GDPs of \$40,000 or above (Investopedia, 2019). Developed countries share several other characteristics namely: (i) They are highly industrialized, (ii) Their birth and death rates are stable. They do not have excessively high birth rates because they have quality medical care and high living standards, infant mortality rates are low. No developed country has an infant mortality rate higher than 10 per 1,000 live births. In terms of life expectancy, all developed countries boast numbers greater than 70 years; many average 80. (iii) They have more women working, particularly in high-ranking executive positions.

Why is entrepreneurship education?

In Nigeria's present economic situation, having knowledge of an academic subject is no longer sufficient for a new graduate. Students are increasingly required to have skills and abilities which will increase their employability, such as: the retrieval and handling of information; communication and presentation; planning and problem solving; and social development and interaction (MATEC, 2019). Entrepreneurial education and training provides individuals with the ability to recognize commercial opportunities, self-esteem, knowledge and skills to act on them. It includes instruction in opportunity recognition, commercializing a concept, managing resources, and initiating a business venture. It also includes instruction in traditional business disciplines such as management, marketing, information systems and finance. Entrepreneurs or the move towards self-employment is, and will continue to become, an increasingly important element of

economic growth and development. It is essential to have the infrastructure required to facilitate entrepreneurial mind-set and encourage self-employment. Having a culture of the creation of a new enterprise is a critical aspect of this infrastructure, as it will encourage students to take the risk of starting a business. Young people with entrepreneurship education are more likely to set up their own companies. Up to 20% of students who participate in a mini-company programme in secondary school will later start their own company (European Union Commission, 2019).

Entrepreneurial Education in Nigeria in Historical Perspective

Entrepreneurship education was introduced in the United States in the 1940s. Over the years (Tulgan, 1999). The concept and content has been expanded, adopted and integrated into the education curricula of other countries. EED has become such an important component of formal education that in 1998, UNESCO World Conference recognized its value and advocated cultivating entrepreneurship and skills in higher education as a development strategy for many emerging economies (UNESCO 2008). The UNESCO report highlighted that through EEd students are able to gain experiences that give them the ability and vision of how to access and transform opportunities of different kinds. This presupposes that EEd goes beyond formal classroom teaching to incorporate training to increase students' ability to anticipate and respond to societal changes for business creation. Tulgan (1999) outlined the functional basis of EEd as education and training which allows students to develop and use their creativity in entrepreneurial development of the country.

In 2006, the government of Nigeria announced the introduction of EED as entrepreneurship studies, to be integrated in the University curriculum as a compulsory course for students irrespective of area of specialization (Okojie, 2009). Effectively, the implementation started in the 2007/2008 academic session. In pursuance of the full implementation of EED, most of universities established a coordinating center for entrepreneurship education to support students' training. The Nigerian University Commission (NUC) was given presidential directives by the Ministry of Education to supervise and coordinate the programme of introducing EEd in Nigerian institutions of high learning (Okojie 2009). At inception, EEd was harped as the panacea for youth unemployment and a catalyst for sustained private sector-led growth. EEd was introduced to provide students in tertiary institutions with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of ventures. To make the delivery effective, the NUC prescribed the following ten areas in the Benchmark Minimum Academic Standard (BEMAS) guide for teaching EED in Nigerian Universities: (1) Introduction to entrepreneurship (2) Entrepreneurship in theory and practice (3) Types of business, staffing and marketing (4) Capital requirement and raising capital (5) Financial planning and management (6) Feasibility studies and reports (7) Innovations (8) legal issues in business (9) Insurance and environmental consideration, and (10) Possible business opportunities in Nigeria. However, about ten years down the road, the excitement and momentum generated at the introduction of EED have waned as a failed expectation.

Ojeifo (2013) summarizes the objectives of EEd in Nigeria to include (1) Provision of meaningful education for youth which could make them self-reliance and subsequently encourage them to self-dependent (2) Providing graduates with the training and support necessary to help them establish a career in small and medium size business (3) Providing graduates with training skills that will make them meet the manpower needs of the society (4) Providing graduates with enough

training in risk management to make risk bearing possible and easy (5) Stimulate industrial and economic growth of rural and less developed area(6) Providing graduates enough training that will make them creative and innovative in identifying new business opportunities and (7) Providing small and medium sized companies with the opportunity to recruit qualified graduates who have received training and tutoring in the skills relevant for business management. How much of these goals have been realized, is the most important that must be asked?

Findings

The study reveals that entrepreneurship education has impacted national development in the following key areas

1. Economic Development: The profits made by entrepreneurs, payments for the various factors of production by the entrepreneur flow as an increase into the National Income. Increase Gross Domestic Products, National Income etc. help in improving the standard of living of the citizens of the country. The contributions of the SMEs in industrial sector to the Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) are valued at about 37% there by making it the second largest contributor to the Nation's GDP after the oil sector.
1. 2. Creation of Immediate Large-scale Employment: Entrepreneurship results in the creation of small businesses. The labor intensive nature of small businesses enables them creates more jobs than the big businesses. The existence of small scale businesses in the country had provided job and employment to many citizens. Small scale businesses play crucial roles in the economic development of countries. In Nigeria for instance, Small Scale Businesses (SSB) Constitutes 85% of all firms operating in the economy, and like in most other developing countries they employed the largest number of workers. Looking at the definition of SMEs, (generally an umbrella term for firms with less than 250 employees) it then means that 97% of all businesses in Nigeria are "small businesses". The SME sector provides, on average, 50% of Nigeria's employment, and 50% of its industrial output. Increasing number of graduates from increasing number of public and private higher institutions who roam the streets, seeking for placement in the few declared vacancies can avail themselves of the opportunity available to make a living.
2. Reduction in Rural-Urban Drifts: One of the primary objectives of promoting entrepreneurship in developing countries is to check rural-urban drift. The migration of rural dwellers to cities in search of 'white-collar' jobs has resulted in congestion, high incidence of crimes, etc.
3. Development of Local Technological Base: The development of indigenous technological base in Nigeria has been championed by native entrepreneurs; this will help in transferring the much needed technology needed for the rapid transformation of the country.
4. Conservation of Foreign Exchanges: This will result from reduced importation of machineries and equipment, raw materials and payment to foreign experts. We must poise to ask whether the aforementioned are in existence in practical reality in Nigeria.

Challenges Confronting Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria

The focus of this work to reiterate is not just merely the narration and exposition of the meaning of entrepreneur, national development and entrepreneurship education, nor is it to just justify the need for entrepreneurship education. Making an array of the role of entrepreneurship education to national development is not enough. The work wants to assess in practical reality the fundamental preparations / arrangements made for entrepreneurship education required for impart in Nigeria. It is not enough to introduce entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities but one has to ask, how many competent, experienced and efficient entrepreneurial lecturers and instructors do we have in the universities for this kind of education? How exposed are the entrepreneurial lecturers in terms of quality and performance and not just theory? What curricular capacity and methodology of instruction has been developed for entrepreneurship education before its introduction? What infrastructural facilities have the Nigerian government put in place in the universities for the facilitation of entrepreneurship education? Is the Nigerian environment ready to be entrepreneurship friendly? These and so many other factors have eluded entrepreneurship education in Nigeria.

It is in the light of the aforementioned questions that Nwosu, Jonathan C. and John Henry Chukwudi (2018) advanced the following as the challenges facing entrepreneurship education in Nigeria.

- A. Low Competence of Entrepreneurship Education Lecturers/Instructors: The Competence of lecturers and instructors that anchors entrepreneurship education in most universities has been fingered as a reason for the poor quality delivery. There is a dearth of lecturers and instructors with practical training in entrepreneurship education or entrepreneurship. In contrast, in Nigeria, the majority of entrepreneurship instructors are from traditional disciplines such as economics or business administration.
- B. Absence of Curricular Capacity to Support the Training: The absence of a curricular guide to inform a pedagogical delivery in the methodology of entrepreneurship education is identified by many researchers as a major drawback in the system. It has also been reported that the existing University curriculum structure has a start up challenge for entrepreneurship education. The NUC benchmark for entrepreneurship education is 6 credits hour, but due to the bloated existing credit loading most of the Universities cannot accommodate the 6 hours and as such entrepreneurship education is taught as a onetime 2 credits hour with a very shallow content.
- C. Poor Infrastructural Support: Poor availability of infrastructure for entrepreneurship education to deliver quality and practical oriented entrepreneurship education requires huge investment in capital. Inadequate funding is indicted in the poor infrastructural support entrepreneurship education to drive quality delivery of entrepreneurship education. Both hard and soft infrastructure is entrepreneurship education as prop for the International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology, Vol. 9, No. 5, October 2018 191system. This limitation subsequently frustrates the integration of entrepreneurship in academic programs in Nigerian universities.
- D. Non-Favourable Policy Environment and Lack of Government Support: There have being lapses in the policy framework to serve as lunch-pad for the entrepreneurial

skills acquired in school, which may be the reason for the lack of entrepreneurial drive among school leavers. Lack of access to credit/ loan, absence of tax rebates, mass poverty, high level of inflation, technological infraction, political instability and insecurity of lives and properties are some of the manifestations of the absence of this entrepreneurship education support.

- E. Teaching Methodology Adopted during Entrepreneurship Education: The current teaching methodology adopted in entrepreneurship education has been described as a mechanistic delivery, which leaves no room for the students to engage individually with the hard realities of the business environment. The high student's/lecturer ratio in Universities occasioned by expanded admission quotas; usually beyond the carrying capacities of the facilities available has been suggested as the reason for de-emphasizing the practical components. The absence of co-curricular activities such as entrepreneurship clubs, lectures and speakers, workshops and seminars, business plan competitions, internships, and venture incubators are key drawbacks of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria.
- F. Absence of Research Support and Linkages: At commencement, it was envisaged that entrepreneurship education will leverage on products of students researches in the Universities. There is a pronounced absence of research support and most of the research endeavours of the students are not targeted and are not applied to real life adoption. Absence of adequate funding, research capacities and linkage opportunities are obvious reasons for this limitation.

Suggestions

From the array of challenges facing entrepreneurship education outlined by Nwosu, Jonathan C. and John Henry Chukwudi (2018), the following deductions could be made suggestions to challenges to entrepreneurship education in Nigeria

- (i) There should be some form of genuine school-work based learning incorporated in some studies as part of the national economic development strategies. This implies enriching the curriculum to incorporate more vocational and technical training. The development of apprenticeship scheme would give new graduates some work skills and experiences.
- (ii) There should be School-based enterprises where students identify potential business, plan, create and operate small business by using the school as mini-incubators.
- (iii) Government should establish small business schools where interested students and community members can participate. This will make students to be self-reliant.
- (iv) Government should develop entrepreneur internship programme by matching students with locally successful entrepreneurs with clearly established education programmes.
- (v) The Government should establish an enterprise college aimed at fostering the specific skills required for entrepreneurship. This will serve as skill-acquisition centre for the youths.
- (vi) Government should create an economic friendly environment that centres on reduction of taxes on small scale businesses.

Conclusion

Education is the clearest path to individual opportunity and societal growth, and entrepreneurship education is especially vital to fuelling a more robust global economy. Entrepreneurs bring new ideas to life through innovation, creativity and the desire to build something of lasting value. Therefore, it is necessary to emphasize more on Entrepreneurship education by teaching undergraduates entrepreneurship skills for entrepreneurship education for them to not just be job seekers, but rather to be job creators. Poor standard of the state of the university in Nigeria is also a contributing factor of entrepreneurship education. Entrepreneurship education could help to reduce the high rate of unemployment in both urban and rural areas of Nigeria, by equipping students with the knowledge and skills for setting up and running small businesses effectively. Entrepreneurship education, however, is not only about pursuing economic ends; it also helps learners to develop entrepreneurial or problem-solving skills they could use in addressing personal and social challenges.

References

1. Adenike Adetola Agbonlahor (2018). Challenges of Entrepreneurial Education in Nigerian Universities: Towards a Repositioning for Impact Federal College of Education, Abeokuta, Nigeria <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/c6e0/32b5345708d0b3f610947a1b052cb10fe954>. Retrieved 29/11/19
2. Balaji Viswanathan (2013). *What is the true measure of our national development?* <https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-true-measure-of-our-national-development>. Retrieved 29/11/19
3. ENTREPRENEURS (2019), *Information About A Career As An Entrepreneur* https://study.com/articles/Entrepreneurs_Information_About_a_Career_as_an_Entrepreneur.html. Retrieved 29/11/19
4. European Union Commission: *Entrepreneurship Education In All Levels In Europe* https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/promoting-entrepreneurship/support/education_en. Retrieved 29/11/19
5. Investopedia. (2019). *Top Developed and Developing Countries*. <https://www.investopedia.com/updates/top-developing-countries/> Retrieved 29/11/19
6. Matec (2018). *Benefits of entrepreneurship education web of Conferences* 121 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319023075_Benefits_of_entrepreneurship_education_and_training_for_engineering_students Retrieved 29/11/19
7. Nwosu, B. & Ohia, A. (2009). Managing entrepreneurship education at the university level in Nigeria: A panacea for graduate self-employment. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 3(2): 49-53.
8. Nwosu, Jonathan C. & John Henry Chukwud (2018). Entrepreneurship Education and the Challenges of Graduate Employability in Nigeria. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328190004> Retrieved 29/11/19
9. Ojeifo S. A. (2013). Entrepreneurship Education In Nigeria: A Panacea For Youth Unemployment, *Journal of Education and Practice Vol. 4, No. 6, 2013*,
10. Okah, R. & Odelola, J.A. (2009). Entrepreneurship education at tertiary level in rivers state: A situational

- analysis. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 3(2): 108- 121.
11. Okojie, J.A. (2009). *Imperative of the Federal Government Directive On The Establishment of Entrepreneurship Studies in Nigerian Universities*. A Paper Presented at the 1st Conference on Effective Implementation of Federal Government Seven-Point Agenda Held at NUC, Abuja, Feb.4-6
 12. Sarma (2018). *National development: meaning, scope and different perspectives* from <https://www.quora.com/What-is-national-development>. Retrieved 29/11/19
 13. Singh, P.K. & Sharma, P. (2011). Rural women empowerment through entrepreneurship development. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 1(2): 24-26.
 14. The Consortium for Entrepreneurship Education (2012). *The State of Entrepreneurship Education 2012*, Columbus, OH USA
 15. Tulgan, B. (1999). Generation x: The future is now. *Entrepreneur of the year magazine*. Fall. 42.
 16. Uche, C.M. and Adesope, O.M. (2009). Capacity building for entrepreneurship education: State of the art in university of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 3(2): 86-98.
 17. Unachukwu, G. O (2009). Issues and Challenges in the Development of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria. *An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal, Ethiopia* 3(5)213-226.
 18. UNESCO (2008). *Promoting Entrepreneurship Education in Secondary Schools*. Final report of UNESCO inter-regional Seminar on promoting entrepreneurship education in Secondary Schools, held in Bangkok, Thailand on 11th – 15th February, 2008
 19. Wilson, K. (2008). *Entrepreneurship Education in Europe*. In *Entrepreneurship and Higher Education*; Potter, J.E, Ed.; OECD Publishing: Paris, France, pp. 98–115.
 20. Zhou, M & Haixia Xu (2012). *A Review of Entrepreneurship Education for College Students in China*. *Adm. Sci.* 2012, 2, 82-98